

Support stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9

Deliverable 5.4 Develop the outputs for the work packages

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1 INTRODUCTION

The secretariat of ZEP and IWG9 is involved in all work packages, to ensure coherent delivery of the overall work programme. The secretariat may also be requested by the IWG9 Plenary or the ZEP AC, to provide additional services in support of the work programme, e.g. to develop and deliver reports, papers, consultation responses, meetings, or seminars.

In this report, we detail the work programmes for the full duration of the project as well as additional work items that have been requested by the two plenary bodies of the organisations.

1.1 ZEP / IWG9 Work Programme 2023

The Work Programme for the first full calendar year of the project (Annex A) was discussed and approved in the Advisory Councils of September 2022 and December 2022. The Programme included specific work items that were developed at the request of co-chairs of the ZEP, with the Technology Committee being the most active network.

For a large part, the Programme consisted of pre-defined work items such as

- Responding to consultations and developing position papers on EU policies
- Support for the CCUS Forum
- monitoring progress on R&I for the IWG9
- developing specific deliverables of the project
- setting up the Projects Network (a requirement of the Grant Agreement).

But there were also new workstreams that the secretariat had to initiate and develop, notably:

- A report on transport of CO₂ by ship (published January 2024: <https://zeroemissionsplatform.eu/co2-transport-by-ship-market/>)
- Temporary Working Group on Carbon Dioxide Removal, aiming to put input in the Mission Innovation
- Provide recommendations on CCUS R&I priorities for the Horizon Europe work programme.
- ZEP Position on the NZIA and publication of an open letter with stakeholders in July 2023 on article 18 of the NZIA (<https://zeroemissionsplatform.eu/open-letter-on-article-18-of-the-net-zero-industry-act/>)

1.1.1 Overview of ZEP outputs to the Commission in 2022-2023

The ZEP responded to the following EC policy developments in the second half of 2022 and in the full year of 2023:

Date	Type of output / Topic	Link to ZEP contribution
12-08-2022	Briefing on UK shortlisting 20 CCUS projects	https://zeroemissionsplatform.eu/zep-note-uk-shortlists-20-ccus-projects-for-government-funding/
16-09-2022	Statement on EU emergency intervention in energy markets	https://zeroemissionsplatform.eu/eu-emergency-intervention-in-energy-markets/
29-09-2022	Joint CCSA-ZEP response to ICVCM Consultation	https://zeroemissionsplatform.eu/joint-ccsa-zep-response-to-icvcm-consultation/
03-10-2022	Briefing on EC analysis of London Protocol	https://zeroemissionsplatform.eu/zep-briefing-european-commission-analysis-paper-on-the-london-protocol/
07-11-2022	Briefing on Innovation Fund	https://zeroemissionsplatform.eu/e3-billion-under-the-innovation-fund/
30-11-2022	Briefing on Horizon Europe Work Programme	https://zeroemissionsplatform.eu/horizon-europe-work-programme-2023-2024/
02-12-2022	Statement on intervention in EU ETS	https://zeroemissionsplatform.eu/interference-in-the-eu-ets-risks-delaying-efforts-to-decarbonise/
24-01-2023	Consultation: Competitive bidding under the Innovation Fund	https://zeroemissionsplatform.eu/response-to-consultation-on-competitive-bidding-under-the-innovation-fund/
16-03-2023	Consultation: market needs in Innovation Fund	https://zeroemissionsplatform.eu/response-to-consultation-on-the-market-needs-in-relation-to-the-eu-ets-innovation-fund/
16-03-2023	Consultation: PCI/PMI list	https://zeroemissionsplatform.eu/response-to-the-consultation-on-the-first-union-list-of-pcis-pmis-in-co2-networks-under-the-revised-ten-e/
16-03-2023	Consultation: input on CCS Directive Guidance documents	https://zeroemissionsplatform.eu/response-to-the-call-for-inputs-to-support-the-revision-of-the-ccs-directive-guidance-documents/
16-03-2023	Consultation: Article 6.4 Supervisory Body on carbon removals	https://zeroemissionsplatform.eu/response-to-the-article-6-4-supervisory-body-call-for-views-on-carbon-removals/
24-03-2023	Consultation: CRCF	https://zeroemissionsplatform.eu/response-to-the-call-for-feedback-on-the-eu-certification-framework-for-carbon-removals/

Date	Type of output / Topic	Link to ZEP contribution
29-03-2023	Statement on NZIA	https://zeroemissionsplatform.eu/zep-first-reaction-to-the-net-zero-industry-act/
25-04-2023	Paper on Green Deal Industrial Plan and NZIA	https://zeroemissionsplatform.eu/zep-paper-on-the-green-deal-industrial-plan-and-the-net-zero-industry-act/
25-05-2023	Response to call for input by Article 6.4 Supervisory Body	https://zeroemissionsplatform.eu/response-to-the-call-for-input-on-the-annotated-agenda-and-related-annexes-of-the-5th-meeting-of-the-article-6-4-supervisory-body/
03-07-2023	Response to consultation on EU 2040 Climate Target	https://zeroemissionsplatform.eu/additional-feedback-to-the-public-consultation-on-the-eu-2040-climate-target/
23-08-2023	Response to monitoring emissions within ETS	https://zeroemissionsplatform.eu/zep-feedback-eu-emissions-trading-system-ets-update-of-the-rules-for-monitoring-and-reporting-emissions/
31-08-2023	Feedback on ICMS	https://zeroemissionsplatform.eu/zeps-feedback-to-the-industrial-carbon-management-strategy/

1.2 ZEP / IWG9 Additional Work Programme 2023

Given the strong positive momentum for CCS, the decreased budget for the new EU grant (€1 million over three years for ZEP and IWG9 together compared to previously €1 million each over three years), and strongly increased ZEP member funding, the ZEP AC of March 2023 approved an additional ZEP work programme (WP). The WP was funded separately by ZEP (ZEP-C) members. The aim was to build on and further strengthen the ZEP and IWG9 work programme.

The additional WP can be found back in Annex B.

Following its approval, the secretariat

- Hired an extra full-time employee to work on external relations and public affairs
- Organised the ZEP conference 2023 in Brussels (26 April 2023) with 160 attendees
- Developed and executed a new advocacy and communication strategy
- Increased the visibility of the ZEP on (social) media
- Launched the Projects Network with a two-day event in Rotterdam (24-25 January 2024). This event was originally scheduled for October 2023.

The administrative support was in the end not hired.

1.3 ZEP Future Structure review

As detailed in deliverable 1.3 (Review of the ETIP/IWG9), the ZEP embarked in 2023 on a thorough review of the current structure. The secretariat has continuously supported this review process which was not foreseen in the Grant agreement. A Temporary Working Group on the ZEP Future Structure was installed and supported.

In October and December 2023, ZEP members reviewed the various options on the table (maintaining the status quo, strengthening their organisation or joining forces with an existing trade association). They unanimously decided to go for the second route: strengthening ZEP as a membership organisation that may apply for the grant itself – in case the Commission decides to continue the ETIPs and the SET Plan. ZEP also updated its structure accordingly—a process that was guided and supported by the ZEP Chair.

1.4 ZEP / IWG9 Work Programme 2024

Just as in the 2023 Work Programme, the 2024 version consisted of a mix of ongoing grant-related work items and new work items that were requested by some co-chairs. In this Work Programme, there is no mention though of ‘additional’ activities but rather one programme that is supported by both the ZEP ETIP secretariat (i.c. the CCSA until 30 June 2024) and the staff of the ZEP Communications ASBL.

At the request of the ZEP Secretary General, a division was made between what the ZEP ETIP secretariat would cover and what extra non-grant related ZEP tasks would be taken up by the ZEP Communications ASBL team. The parts of the work programme of 2024 that focused on the Projects Network, the annual ZEP conference and additional communications and advocacy work were taken up by the ZEP Communications ASBL while all work items of the Grant Agreement were taken up by the ZEP ETIP secretariat.

Pre-defined work items were

- Responding to consultations and developing position papers on EU policies
- Support for the CCUS Forum (renamed to ICM Forum)
- monitoring progress on R&I for the IWG9
- developing specific deliverables of the project, notably
 - Review of the SET Plan targets (deliverable 1.4)
 - Report on public perception of CCS (deliverable 2.4)
 - Report on CCS and the Just Transition (deliverable 1.6)

New workstreams / work items for 2024:

- Projects Network launch event (mentioned above, organised by the ZEP ETIP) plus further establishing the Network and plan new events in 2024 (led by ZEP Communications)
- ZEP Conference in December 2024
- Further development of the communications and advocacy strategy (led by ZEP Communications)
- Open letter on IPCEI for CCUS (led by ZEP Communications, supported by ZEP ETIP)
- Analysis of policy and funding priorities of the EU ICMS
- Report on Flexible power with CCS
- Paper on low carbon products

The work on CCS supply chain was halted due to inactivity of the members.

1.4.1 Overview of ZEP outputs to the Commission in 2024

The ZEP responded to the following EC policy developments in 2024:

Date	Type of output / Topic	Link to ZEP contribution
29-01-2024	Statement on support increase of Innovation Fund and Horizon Europe	https://zeroemissionsplatform.eu/zep-statement-step/
31-01-2024	Briefing on ESABCC policy recommendations	https://zeroemissionsplatform.eu/zep-briefing-esabcc-post-2030-climate-policy-recommendations/
01-02-2024	Co-signing of letter on low-carbon products	https://zeroemissionsplatform.eu/open-letter-industry-and-civil-society-calls-on-european-commission-to-develop-strategy-for-low-carbon-products/
06-02-2024	Response to ICMS publication	https://zeroemissionsplatform.eu/zep-welcomes-the-long-awaited-eu-industrial-carbon-management-strategy/
12-02-2024	Briefing on ICMS	https://zeroemissionsplatform.eu/zep-briefing-icms-1/
12-02-2024	Briefing on EU 2040 Climate Target	https://zeroemissionsplatform.eu/zep-briefing-2040-eu-climate-target/
21-03-2024	Detailed response on ICMS	https://zeroemissionsplatform.eu/zeps-response-to-the-industrial-carbon-management-strategy/
22-05-2024	Paper on funding requirements	https://zeroemissionsplatform.eu/zep-paper-on-funding-requirements/
17-06-2024	Open letter on IPCEI for CCUS	https://zeroemissionsplatform.eu/harnessing-ipcei-mechanism-for-ccus/
04-07-2024	Publication of public perception report	https://zeroemissionsplatform.eu/public-perception-key-enablers-and-hurdles-for-ccs-and-ccu-projects/
18-07-2024	Response to the EU ETS revision's condition for permanent storage through carbon capture and utilisation	https://zeroemissionsplatform.eu/zep-response-permanent-ccu-eu-ets/

Date	Type of output / Topic	Link to ZEP contribution
07-10-2024	Recommendations for the certification of carbon removals	https://zeroemissionsplatform.eu/publication/recommendations-for-the-certification-of-carbon-removals/
24-10-2024	Co-signing of open letter on urgent need to scale up Industrial Carbon Management in Europe	https://zeroemissionsplatform.eu/publication/over-50-european-industry-representatives-urge-the-european-commission-to-prioritise-industrial-carbon-management/
25-10-2024	Recommendations on the methodology to determine the greenhouse gas (GHG) emission savings of low-carbon fuels	https://zeroemissionsplatform.eu/publication/recommendations-on-the-methodology-to-determine-the-ghg-emission-savings-of-low-carbon-fuels/

1.5 ZEP / IWG9 2025 Work Programme

After the takeover of ZEP Communications ASBL (ZEP-C) over the SSZEPIWG9 Grant on 1 July 2024, ZEP-C managed both their activities and Grant Agreement activities. The 2025 Work Programme was approved at the 81st Advisory Council and IWG9 Plenary meeting held on 4 December 2024 (and can be found in Annex D).

Many policy developments were planned for 2025, after the 2024 European Elections and the instalment of a new College of Commissioners, and ZEP's and IWG9's 2025 Work Programme reflected that. Policy-related activities include:

- Provide comprehensive input to the European Institutions through position papers
- Schedule meetings with the public representatives from the European Commission and the European Parliament
- Support the preparation of the 2025 ICM Forum Plenary
- Contribute to the future work of the ICM Forum working groups
- Continue providing input on DACCS and BioCCS in the Carbon Removal Expert Group

Within ZEP's structure, the following activities were set out in the work programme:

- The implementation of a Finance Working Group within the Policy & Economics Committee.
- The strengthening of engagement with the European Parliament, establishment of a targeted policy and advocacy strategy, deepening of collaboration with other ICM stakeholders, increasing of ZEP-organised events and the measuring of ZEP's impact, coordinated through the External Relations Committee
- Hosting a successful second instalment of the Projects Network in Ravenna CCS, Italy.

In terms of IWG9 and wider SET-Plan work, ZEP and IWG9 were set to collaborate in the recently established SET Plan Taskforces, more specifically in Task Force 1 on Circularity and materials substitution and Task Force 5 on Access to market.

1.5.1 Overview of ZEP outputs to the Commission in 2025

Date	Type of output / Topic	Link to ZEP contribution
06-02-2025	Co-signing of open letter on CCS in the Clean Industrial Deal	https://zeroemissionsplatform.eu/publication/open-letter-ccs-in-the-clean-industrial-deal/
16-04-2025	Response to the public consultation on oil and gas producer’s contributions to the EU’s 2030 storage objective set out in the NetZero Industry Act	https://zeroemissionsplatform.eu/publication/response-to-the-public-consultation-on-oampgs-contributions-to-the-eus-2030-storage-objective-set-out-in-the-nzia/
21-05-2025	Co-signing of open letter on Research and Innovation in the EU’s Competitiveness Agenda	https://zeroemissionsplatform.eu/publication/open-letter-cleantech-research-innovation-must-sit-at-the-heart-of-the-eus-competitiveness-agenda/
25-04-2025	Response to the public consultation on the draft Clean Industrial Deal State Aid Framework (CISAF)	https://zeroemissionsplatform.eu/publication/response-to-the-public-consultation-on-the-draft-cisaf/

ANNEX A – ZEP IWG9 WORK PROGRAMME 2023

Approved at the December 2022 AC.

The draft joint ZEP and IWG9 work programme, with both common areas and areas that are specific for ZEP and IWG9 respectively, was presented for guidance at the ZEP AC and IWG9 Plenary in September 2022. It has since been discussed with the Networks, Government group, the External Relations Group (ERG) and the Communication Group, resulting in some adjustments. Terms of References (ToR) for the workstreams highlighted in the work programme will, as usual, be drafted for approval. For the immediately upcoming workstreams, draft ToRs have been prepared and discussed with Networks, and are presented for approval under item 4, Network updates, in today’s agenda.

The work programme is a living document based on the EU (and member state) policy agenda with a focus on CCS and CCU, and directly linked to the coordinated ZEP and IWG9 governance structure: the Networks and TWGs, the ERG and Communication Group, and the Government Group.

Focus areas on overarching level

- Coordination and close cooperation between ZEP and the IWG9, to continue providing strong support and input to the CCUS SET-Plan (IWG9) activities – necessary to reach Europe’s ambitious 2030 climate goals – and a high level of coordination with other European and global programmes. A review of the coordination and governance structure will also be in the plans.
- The CCUS Forum is the key vehicle for the EC regarding the development of CCUS in Europe. ZEP is engaged in the Forum working groups (WG) as co-chair of two of the three WGs and an active a member in the third. It is crucial to continue the strong engagement in this work – that includes two of ZEP’s key: an EU strategy for CCS and CCU, and a regulatory framework for CO2 transport infrastructure.
- As more and more CCS/CCU projects are becoming market-ready, there is a need to intensify the support for these projects, cooperate closely and monitor their development.

Delivering on the day-to-day work

Network Policy & Economics (NWPE)

The Network and the TWG Policy & Funding remains the main point of contact for the preparation of responses to consultations and other input to the EC. Focus areas for the NWPE:

- The CCUS Forum and the ongoing and planned working groups: For the consultation on the 2023 EC Communication, CO2 infrastructure, Industrial partnership, and Public awareness. Providing support to the Forum work, with the special aim of enabling an EU strategy for CCS and CCU and the proposed regulatory framework for CO2 transport infrastructure, will be of key importance to maintain the positive momentum and drive implementation.

- The two EC studies – the technical study on CO₂ transport infrastructure and the study on regulatory issues on CO₂ transport and storage infrastructure. The upcoming revision of the National Energy and Climate Plans (NECP).
- Provide insights on EU and national support instruments for CCUS R&I and deployment and how they interact (in cooperation with the Network Technology (NWT)).
- The policy instruments under the ‘Fit for 55 package’, with a focus on the EU ETS, the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism, the Innovation Fund, and the Renewable Energy Directive.
- The upcoming work on a revision of the Monitoring and Reporting Regulation.
- Follow and contribute to the revision of the CO₂ Storage Directive Guidance Documents ([link](#)). The NWT will focus on technical aspects and the NWPE will support on regulatory and funding aspects.
- CO₂ transport by ship, follow-up from the first WG on CO₂ transport by ship. The aim is to investigate the scope and trade routes for CO₂ ship transport, follow up on interoperability and the work done by ISO, IMO, and SIGTTO, address existing barriers to commercialisation, and identify possible work needed for a Europe-wide CO₂ storage market.

Network Technology (NWT)

The Network will continue its very active work programme, engaging experts from members and observers on technical aspects regarding deployment of CCS and CCU. Focus areas for the NWT:

- Carbon Dioxide Removals (CDR) – The TWG CDR will continue to follow and give input to the ongoing international work of Mission Innovation on CDR. Moreover, it will follow up on the Communication on Sustainable Carbon Cycles – notably, the recently adopted EC proposal on a certification framework for carbon removals, incentive schemes, the development of voluntary carbon markets, accounting, standards and methodologies, including compliance with article 6 of the Paris Agreement. The TWG will be the central focus for ZEP’s work on CDR and will be supported by the NWPE.
- Recommendations on CCUS R&I priorities for the Horizon Europe work programme.
- Progress review and recommendations on the key IWG9 R&I activities. The plan is to have six reports updating R&I activities over the coming three years, starting with a report focused on CO₂ transport infrastructure and PCIs (2023). For 2024 and 2025 there will be reports on Capture, Storage, Utilisation, Commercial-scale CCS and Linking EU and national strategies and plans on CCS and CCU. These reports will follow up and be based on the eight R&I activities reports prepared by the IWG9.
- Analysis of the implications that the energy crisis – specifically the reduced access to energy – will have on the different CCS and CCU technologies (and thus the transition towards net-zero).
- Analysis of the risks involved in the CCUS supply chain – including materials, technology, and expertise
- Follow and provide input on the EC/JRC technical study on optimal CO₂ networks.

- Provide guidance and input to the CCUS Forum Working Group on CO₂ infrastructure, regarding CO₂ specifications in the context of an integrated European CO₂ transport and storage network. The aim is to build a common understanding on CO₂ specifications along the value chain. The focus will be on the need for standards and the framework under which such these could be developed. How this work will be set up and undertaken will be discussed with the Network Technology co-chairs.
- Follow and contribute to the revision of the CO₂ Storage Directive Guidance Documents ([link](#)). The NWT will focus on technical aspects and the NWPE will support on regulatory and funding aspects.
- The NWT will support the TWG on CO₂ transport by ship regarding objective 1 and 2 of the appended

New Network Projects (depending on other EU grants)

Creation of this Network in the ZEP structure will depend on the extent to which other EU grants cover this topic. Focus areas for this Network:

- *Supporting market-ready projects from a policy, funding and technological point of view*
- *Addressing existing barriers*
- *Improving public perception, and*
- *Enabling knowledge sharing.*

External Relations Group (ERG)

For the areas of specific interest for ZEP – highlighted above – the ERG will guide communications and outreach activities. Given the many ongoing EU policy initiatives and legislative processes, the initial focus of communications for end-2022 and 2023 will be to secure meetings with policymakers and provide input to EU policy initiatives. In parallel, the ERG will guide the execution – on behalf of the AC – of the communications and dissemination activities connected to the ZEP reports, hosting events and webinars, and communicating through social media and the newsletter. The ZEP Communications Group will play an important role here, as a direct channel to the wider group of members for coordination and information exchange on messages and activities.

Government Group

With several countries preparing national strategies for CCUS and an increasing number of ongoing and planned CCUS projects across Europe, the ZEP Government Group – where the interest from member states and permanent representations is growing – will be crucial in the coordination between EU and national strategies, policies, and funding opportunities.

ANNEX B – ZEP ADDITIONAL WORK PROGRAMME 2023

Approved by the ZEP AC in March 2023.

Focus and funding for the additional work programme

The ACEC has discussed and proposed the following: Referring to the strong positive momentum and extremely busy policy agenda, the focus for the ZEP additional WP should be to strengthen visibility, communication, and public affairs based on the work programme as approved by the AC73 in December 2023, with an extra focus on the CCS/CCU Communication at the end of 2023, the Green Deal Industrial Plan/the Net Zero Industry Act, and the European Parliament elections/European Commission renewal in 2024.

This is proposed:

- Additional resource (one FTE) to the ZEP secretariat, focused on external relations and Public Affairs (€65,000 counted on a yearly basis)
- Additional activities on visibility (€60,000):
 - Enhanced advocacy and communication activities, including increased media and social media presence and enhanced material dissemination
 - Increased number of external events and increased participation in external events
- To showcase the positive CCS/CCU narrative and drive the important items of development and deployment of CCS and CCU – an EU CCS/CCU strategy, Europe-wide CO₂ transport and storage infrastructure, national strategies for CCS and CCU, improved geographical spread, investability, adequate business models.
- The strong increase in activities and the increase in membership calls for dedicated administrative support (one PTE) (€20,000).

New Network Projects

ZEP AC has approved for ZEP to include a new Network Projects, in parallel with the Networks Policy & Economics and Technology, to support the many CCS/CCU projects, address existing barriers, improve public perception, and enable real project-to-project knowledge sharing.

The need to support the market-ready projects is also obvious, taking into account the ongoing activities to create EC based CCUS Industrial partnerships, and the Industrial/CO₂ capture coalition funded by the European Climate Foundation that is expected to start shortly.

This new Network Projects addresses the obvious gap in the CCS/CCU deployment in Europe – there is no EU/EEA-wide platform that specifically caters to the numerous projects in the pipeline. It is vital for the CCS/CCU community to coordinate actions as best as possible, not to create singular entities and overlaps that will lead to inefficiency and counterproductivity.

By introducing this network, ZEP establishes an important tool to efficiently support projects and, at the same time, actively help the EC and European governments regarding necessary policy/regulation, funding and actions linked to public perception.

Objective – The objective is to support market-ready projects:

- Address on-the-ground enablers and barriers – discuss and share with public authorities,
- Enable real project-to-project knowledge sharing (consider competition law and confidentiality) on good practices and experiences (e.g., permitting, licencing, PCI/funding processes),
- Improve public perception,
- Having both closed and open sessions – on EU as well as regional level,
- De-risking projects, focusing on specific regions,
- Organise site visits for EC and national government officials,
- Use learnings from earlier project knowledge sharing experience.

Composition:

- Co-chairs for network and sessions: project promoters/managers (and possibly representatives from the EC)
- Project representatives (technical and commercial), take into account also newcomers and smaller/remote emitters, and industrial hubs and clusters,
- Governments and public authorities (also link to/sharing and discussing with the ZEP Government Group),
- Link to the research community (demo and scale-up resulting in further need for R&I).

The aim is for the ACEC – supported by the Networks, ERG, and Government Group – to prepare the Network including co-chairs in order to start the Network in July 2023.

ANNEX C – ZEP IWG9 WORK PROGRAMME 2024

Approved at the ZEP AC of December 2023.

Introduction

2024 will be an important year for the carbon capture and storage (CCS) community in Europe. The spade will go into the ground for the first commercial CCS site in the EU (Porthos in the Netherlands), Northern Lights will become the first project to deliver cross-border CO₂ transport and storage, the European Commission launches the long-awaited Industrial Carbon Management Strategy, there are elections for the European Parliament and Member States need to review their National Energy and Climate Plans. After many lost years, CCS seems to finally be moving from development to deployment as a key technology to drive the decarbonisation of Europe's hard-to-abate sectors.

The Zero Emissions Platform (ZEP) and the Implementation Working Group 9 of the SET-Plan (IWG9) are at the forefront of CCS policy making, on the one hand as the trusted advisors to the EU and as Member States working collectively to achieve Europe's climate goals – notably on the decarbonisation of the energy intensive industries. In this document, we provide an outline of our main activities for 2024.

The governance structures of ZEP and IWG9 are largely merged, and their secretariat is funded by a single Horizon Europe grant (running from July 2022 to June 2025), hence the choice for a joint work programme. We will also include those activities that are *de facto* funded by the members of ZEP, resulting in extra bandwidth for a programme that goes beyond the deliverables set out in the Horizon Europe grant agreement. For the sake of clarity, those deliverables for 2024 will be spelt out in detail below.

The work programme should be considered as a living and reference document, especially for those active in the various working groups as well as for the secretariat and the organisations executing the grant. It could also be changed depending on the outcome of the ZEP restructuring – a process underway now and should be implemented in 2024. As ZEP aims to strengthen its advocacy and communications workstream, this could alter the goals and deliverables of this work programme. Hence, a certain amount of flexibility and agility should be taken into account.

1 Main Policy Developments in 2024

Before we dive into the work streams, let's zoom out and look at the main CCS and CCU related policy developments that we expect to happen in 2024.

In Q1 2024, the European Commission is expected to publish a proposal for an EU 2040 climate target. ZEP expects the proposal to provide further clarity on the role of CCS and CCU in contributing to the EU's climate targets, seeks to inform the co-decision process on the 2040 target and contribute to the upcoming legislative processes where existing EU legislation will be aligned with the 2040 target.

The 2040 climate target proposal will be complemented by an **Industrial Carbon Management Strategy** (ICMS). The ICMS will assess what role CCS and CCU technologies can play in reducing and removing emissions in the EU economy until 2050, as well as what measures are needed to scale them up, including in the deployment of EU-wide CO₂ transport and storage infrastructures. This strategy will be crucial to set out the European Commission's vision on the role of CCS in Europe and what policy measures are needed to achieve this vision. The new Commission, expected to start at the end of 2024, is expected to propose policy initiatives supporting CCS.

- ZEP will continue to advocate for a strong ICMS in line with ZEP's recommendations on the strategy, as specified in [the contribution](#) to the ICMS consultation of 2023.
- ZEP will advocate for a consultation to be opened following the publication of the strategy and respond to it.
- ZEP will engage with and support the Commission in the deliverables and initiatives proposed in the ICMS, provided that these align and enhance the deployment of CCS and CCU technologies

A landmark piece of legislation for CCS will undoubtedly be the **Net Zero Industry Act**, proposed by the Commission in early 2023. This proposal for a regulation will be under negotiation between the EU institutions (trilogues) in late 2023/early 2024. The two key elements in the NZIA are the 50Mt CO₂ annual injection capacity target for the EU in 2030 and its Article 18. Together with other stakeholders, the ZEP published [an open letter](#) in July 2023 calling for an implementable and pragmatic Net Zero Industry Act Article 18.

- ZEP will continue its support for the NZIA as it will spur the deployment of CCS in Europe. The NZIA should be approved before the **2024 European Parliament** elections. ZEP will insist on this timeline in its contact with policymakers.
- ZEP will make recommendations to the three institutions during the trilogues regarding the provisions best placed to support CCS deployment in Europe.

The European Parliament elections will take place from 6 to 9 June 2024. A new European Parliament entails a new European Commission. Both institutions will play a critical role in translating the 2040 climate targets into the right political and regulatory framework. As CCS will play an important role in achieving these climate targets, the Zero Emissions Platform seeks a (pro)active dialogue with the Commission and the Parliament, pushing for an ambitious CCS agenda in the next EU legislative cycle. The ICMS is an obvious lever for such an agenda, but more political pressure will be needed.

- ZEP will further develop its advocacy and communications strategy and undertake efforts to have CCS represented in programmes of the main European political parties and the new European Commission's policy agenda.
- ZEP will engage with EU policymakers ahead of the elections to highlight the importance of CCS and CCU deployment and the need to develop EU and national funding programmes that fit the requirements to reach climate neutrality by 2050.

On the national level, EU member states are required to send updated **National Energy and Climate Plans (NECPs)** to the Commission. The Guidance to Member States encourages national governments to include CCS provisions¹. Several Member States are in the process of developing their own carbon management strategies, such as Germany and France, while others are only beginning to explore CCS strategies (such as Spain).

- Together with other stakeholders, ZEP will analyse the updated NECPs and provide feedback on those NECPs where policies are insufficient and/or lacking.
- Pending internal capacity, ZEP will work with national governments to support them in their development of national carbon management strategies.

The European Commission published the Strategic Technologies for Europe Platform (STEP) proposal for a regulation at the end of June 2023 to support investments in critical technologies, such as CCS and CCU. An agreement on this proposal could take place in Q1 2024.

- ZEP will monitor the legislative progress of the STEP proposal and support the increase in the Innovation Fund and Horizon Europe programmes.
- ZEP will support the STEP proposal and highlight the need to develop EU and national funding programmes and to incentivise investments in line with the funding required for CCS to reach the 2040 and 2050 climate targets.

2 CCUS Forum

ZEP is one of the co-chairs of the CCUS Forum working group on CO₂ infrastructure and has contributed to several CCUS Forum working groups.

- ZEP will support the preparation of the 2024 plenary.
- ZEP will support and contribute to the potential future work of the CCUS Forum working group on CO₂ infrastructure and the CCUS Forum expert group on CO₂ specifications.

3 CDR

The European Commission published a proposal for a regulation on an EU certification for carbon removals in November 2022. Trilogues on the proposal have started start in Q4 2023 and policymakers are committed to reach an agreement before the European Parliament recesses in March 2024. Following the adoption of the regulation, the European Commission, in collaboration with a dedicated expert group, will

¹ [Guidance to Member States for updated NECPs 2021-2030](#), European Commission.

work on the preparation of a methodologies for carbon dioxide removals (CDR) certification framework throughout 2024.

- ZEP will closely monitor the progress of the proposal and make policy recommendations
- ZEP will contribute to the preparation of a CDR methodologies via its representative in the Expert Group, Kristin Jordal, and by responding to future potential calls for inputs.

ZEP will also follow the adoption of delegated acts amending the EU ETS Monitoring and Reporting Regulation and relevant for CCS and CCU deployment.

Finally, ZEP will closely monitor developments related to key EU funding programmes, including the Connecting Europe Facility, the Innovation Fund, Horizon Europe, and LIFE.

4 ZEP and IWG9 Working Groups

Several hundreds of CCS experts meet regularly in meetings that the secretariat organises – mostly in the context of ZEP but also in combined sessions with IWG9 delegates. The main meetings continue to be the **Advisory Council** which gathers four times per year and is attended by ZEP members, the IWG9 constituency but also by interested parties that are not formally connected to either organisation. In June 2024, the Advisory Council will include a meeting of the **ZEP Communications ASBL** that gathers once a year. (This is the Belgian non-profit organisation with a membership structure that sponsors the ZEP secretariat and additional activities, on top of the EU grant)

Depending on political and economic developments, these are the most important work items per forum. The ZEP secretariat runs several bodies where members meet, both of the ZEP and of IWG9: Committees, Temporary Working Groups (which fall under Committees), and a new Projects Network. It also provides the secretariat for the ZEP Government Group, which consists of representatives of around twenty European governments.

5 Policy & Economics Committee

The Policy & Economics Committee (PEC) will organise four meetings in 2024, it has so far not been decided if any of the meetings will be in person, most meetings will be virtual.

PEC will in 2024 in particular analyse and evaluate together with its members and the working group on policy and funding upcoming proposed priorities in the EU ICMS, as well as the needs and priorities which should be set by the new European Commission following the European Parliamentary elections.

The PEC and its working group will analyse and further identify needs for public funding or other support mechanisms to derisk investments in the full CCS value chain to enable industrial decarbonisation, in cooperation with the newly established projects network.

6 Technology Committee

The Technology Committee (TC) will organise four meetings in 2024; the meeting taking place in or close to September will be an in-person meeting in Brussels; the other three will be virtual meetings.

Mission Innovation CDR. TC supports the EC in their participation in Mission Innovation on CDR. This has been an ongoing activity in 2023 and will be continued in 2024. The TWG CDR will meet regularly, guided by activities in the MI CDR. The work in the Removals Expert Group is part of this activity.

Two reports are currently in the pipeline. The TWGs will continue their work and finalise their reports in 2024.

- 1. Flexible power with CCS** (tbc, co-leads Arthur Heberle, Robert de Kler)
- 2. CCS Supply chain** (co-leads Charles Soothill, Arthur Heberle)

Topics for approval by the AC:

- 1. Transport cost:** recent publications suggest that transport costs for landlocked emitters may reach €200/t, for the CO₂ to reach a coastline by rail and/or pipeline. A ZEP paper could be written on this topic, to highlight the issues and suggest ways forward (e.g., stressing the need for onshore storage). Just as with the aforementioned two reports, there is a capacity issue within the secretariat
- 2. CO₂ specifications:** way forward. Recent development in the knowledge of the effects of and behaviour of impurities in CO₂ streams have led to strict specifications. This leads to increasing cost of purification for emitters, potentially making CCS unaffordable. A two-pipe solution to handle captured CO₂ from different capture technologies has also been suggested. The CCUS Forum expert group that produced the report for the CCUS-Forum could be invited to reflect on these issues.

7 Projects Network

In 2023 ZEP created the Projects Network that will support the many ongoing and planned CCS and CCU projects in Europe. The Network should also address existing barriers and help de-risking investments, improve public perception of CCS, and enable real project-to-project knowledge sharing. By introducing this network, ZEP establishes an important tool to efficiently support projects and, at the same time, actively help the EC and European governments regarding necessary policy/regulation, funding and actions linked to public perception.

The Projects Network is in development and will be launched officially at the Porthos site in Rotterdam, 24-25 January 2024. For the rest of the year, one or two more of such events could be organised in order to facilitate the exchange of knowledge among project developers and keep the momentum.

At the CCUS Forum 2023, the European Commission unveiled plans to launch their own industrial carbon management knowledge sharing network where participation will be mandatory for projects that have received EU funding, and voluntary and encouraged for others. Once the ICMS has been published and further details are known, ZEP will explore the options of informing this new initiative via its own Projects Network experience to date and if dedicated funding is available, consider bidding to provide the secretariat for the Commission's network, streamlining the two initiatives into one.

The current ZEP Project Network does not have dedicated funding source, has been having challenges in confirming co-chairs and the detailed governance structure is yet to be established. However, if the future entails joining forces with the European Commission's network, these challenges would be addressed.

8 External Relations Committee

The External Relations Group plays a crucial role in providing strategic guidance to ZEP's external communications activities, as well as in promoting ZEP's mission and identity across its wide network of stakeholders. The ERG co-chairs also contribute to the development of external engagements with policymakers and are able to represent ZEP at these meetings.

Effective coordination between ERG and ACEC as well as the other committees is important to ensure the external facing activities are timely, focussed and effective.

Three main pillars identified:

1) Organisational (internal)

- Work on clear Terms of Reference and Governance for ERG in its new configuration
- Ensure that interaction /coordination with the other ZEP Committees is clearly organised, efficient, and effective (e.g. with ACEC, Policy & Economics, Government, etc)

2) External – socialisation of Policy /Technical work of ZEP Committees with relevant stakeholders

- Develop and tailor an advocacy and communication plan based on the work program of the ZEP Committees by its January 2023 meeting – the plan needs to be fit for purpose and not too generic
- Ensure a thorough review of the communication tools and practices (stakeholder mapping, messaging, use of social media, website, etc) to ensure an effective implementation of the external relations and communication program

3) External: Assess potential role of ZEP in the area of public acceptance:

- Education (for example in the Parliament after elections, with local authorities in Member states, in schools and universities)
- Support (including to authorities / local authorities) with communication materials, events, etc to reach the general public

As highlighted in the introduction, the work programme covers activities funded by the Horizon Europe grant and those funded by member sponsorships to ZEP-Communications ABSL. Following from “additional work programme”, adopted by ZEP for 2023 for activities funded by member sponsorships, the 2024 work programme covers all both grant- and member-funded activities. In 2023, the focus of activities funded by member sponsorships was advocacy, communications, events and visibility. 2024 work programme continues this approach, and these activities are likely to overwhelmingly fit under the External Relation Committee’s activities:

- Establishing an advocacy and communications implementation plan with clear KPIs
 - Establishing specific goals for engaging with policymakers on CCS-related policy files
 - Establishing renewed brand voice and messages for ZEP that is used uniformly in all communication – what the organisation does, its principles, its value proposition for members
 - Increase ZEP visibility across social media platforms
 - Explore rebranding ZEP and revamping ZEP website
 - Raising the profile of CCS as a climate technology
- Organising annual ZEP CCS Conference on 24 April 2024

9 Research and Innovation

The [SET plan activities](#) are clustered into 10 actions for research and innovation, whereas CCUS is number 9 (thereby the number 9 in the SET Plan Implementation Working Group, IWG, for CCUS). The [CCUS SET Plan Implementation Working Group \(IWG9\)](#) is chaired by the Netherlands, Norway and Zero Emissions Platform (ZEP) and established a few years ago ambitious 2030 targets and R&I activities. These are now ready for updating – and this work will be carried out in 2024. An important part of the ZEP/IWG9 work is to advance the research and innovation agenda of CC(U)S in Europe. Notably within the IWG9 context, European countries should be more involved and exchange their latest insights of R&I projects.

At the EU grant preceding the current one for the secretariat of IWG9, a clear research agenda was spelled out; below follows a similar structure to organise the ZEP/IWG9 in this respect. Notably, ZEP will support the realisation of the SET Plan Implementation Plan on CCS and CCU which has defined eight key R&I activities with ten linked targets to be met.

The secretariat will increase its engagement with European governments to find more CCS R&I contact points and add these to our distribution lists. The R&I activities included in the existing [SET Plan Implementation Plan for CCUS](#), and that need to be updated, are the following (in brackets are reference made to R&I targets to be explained in the following section):

- R&I Activity 1: Delivery of a whole chain CCS project operating in the power sector (target 1).
- R&I Activity 2: Delivery of regional CCS and CCU clusters, including feasibility for a European hydrogen infrastructure (targets 2 & 3 and 10).
- R&I Activity 3: EU Projects of Common Interest for CO₂ transport infrastructure (target 4).
- R&I Activity 4: Establish a European CO₂ Storage Atlas (target 5).
- R&I Activity 5: Unlocking European Storage capacity (target 7).
- R&I Activity 6: Developing next-generation CO₂ capture technologies (target 6).
- R&I Activity 7: CCU Action (targets 8 & 9).
- R&I Activity 8: Understanding and communicating the role of CCS and CCU in meeting European and national energy and climate change goals (target 10).

ANNEX D – ZEP IWG9 WORK PROGRAMME 2025

Approved at the 81st Advisory Council and IWG9 Plenary of December 2024.

1. Introduction

The European Technology Innovation Platforms-ZEP (ETIP-ZEP) and the Implementation Working Group 9 of the SET-Plan (IWG9) form the key bodies involved in the assessment of deployment of carbon capture and storage (CCS) and carbon capture and utilization (CCU) under the Strategic Energy Technology Plan (SET-Plan). For nearly 20 years, ETIP-ZEP and IWG9 have monitored the progress of deployment of these key technologies, presenting recommendations to the Commission and Member States on the actions needed to accelerate their deployment.

The governance structures of ETIP-ZEP and IWG9 are largely merged, and their secretariat, run provided by the Zero Emissions Platform, is funded by the SSZEPIWG9 grant which runs to June 2025.

This paper presents the work programme for 2025, detailing the activities of ETIP-ZEP and the IWG9. The paper should be considered as a living and reference document and more details on the specific activities of the ETIP-ZEP Committees will be presented to participants in early 2025. This is particularly due to the changes in the make-up of the co-chairs of those Committees and the commencement of the next Commission, thus making it currently unclear how the policy cycle will proceed.

2. Policy developments for industrial carbon management in 2025

Following several years of increasing political momentum for CCS and CCU, 2025 looks set to be a pivotal year for CCS and CCU policy at the EU level. In December 2024, the European Commission will take office for the next mandate until 2029.

Following the publication of the Industrial Carbon Management Strategy (ICMS) in February 2024, there is a clear mandate for political action on industrial carbon management for the incoming Commission. The Commissioner mission letters have a clear focus on addressing key issues such as developing a CO₂ market, addressing regulatory barriers, focusing on the deployment of transport and storage infrastructure, and accelerating demand for low carbon industrial products and services, which industrial carbon management can provide.

Among the policies where ETIP-ZEP's Committees will be active are:

2.1 Clean Industrial Deal

In December 2024, the Commission will publish a Communication outlining the key priorities for a Clean Industrial Deal (CID). The CID will focus on accelerating the decarbonisation of European industries and ensuring their competitiveness, in order to preserve industrial production in the EU. A key focus of the CID will be on lowering energy prices, deploying strategic technologies like CCS and CCU, accelerating lead markets for low carbon products, and the buildout of critical infrastructure such as CO₂ transport and storage infrastructure.

To this end, ETIP-ZEP will:

- Provide comprehensive input to the European Commission with a position paper
- Schedule meetings with the Commission to discuss these issues.

2.2 European Parliament Own-initiative Procedure (INI)

In 2025, the European Parliament will look to provide its initiative report (INI) on industrial carbon management (ICM) outlining the key actions required by the Commission to deliver on the climate targets for 2040 and 2050 and a Clean Industrial Deal.

To this end, ETIP-ZEP will:

- Provide comprehensive input to the European Parliament with a position paper
- Schedule meetings with key MEPs and assistants, along with members, to discuss these issues.

2.3 Net Zero Industry Act (NZIA)

Finalised in 2024, the Net Zero Industry Act (NZIA) provides for a comprehensive framework to accelerate the deployment of strategic net zero technologies including CCS and CCU. Among the provisions in the NZIA are measures to accelerate the manufacturing and deployment of net zero technologies and projects. Additionally, Chapter 3 is devoted to accelerating the development of CO₂ storage capacity.

In 2025 a number of pieces of implementing legislation are to be provided by the Commission including:

- Delegated Act on primarily used components for strategic net zero technologies
- Delegated Act on 'main specific components'
- Delegated Act on CO₂ storage obligations for oil and gas producers

To this end, ETIP-ZEP envisages to:

- Provide comprehensive input to the European Commission with position papers
- Schedule meetings with the Commission to discuss these issues

2.4 Industrial Carbon Management (ICM) Forum

In 2024 ZEP contributed to several ICM Forum working groups and the ICM Plenary. In 2025 ZEP envisages to:

1. Support the preparation of the 2025 plenary.
2. Support and contribute to the potential future work of the ICM Forum working groups

2.5 Carbon Removal and Carbon Farming Regulation (CRCF)

In November 2024, the Carbon Removal and Carbon Farming Regulation (CRCF) was approved by the Council of the European Union and entered into force. As part of the CRCF, draft methodologies on carbon removals will be prepared by the Commission. The process for the creation thereof began in 2024, starting with the methodologies for Direct Air Capture and Storage (DACCS) and Biogenic CO₂ capture with storage (BioCCS). In 2024, ETIP-ZEP drafted a report on recommendations for these methodologies which was also shared with the Carbon Removal Expert Group.

In 2025, ETIP-ZEP will continue to:

- Provide input on the draft methodologies for DACCS and BioCCS in the Carbon Removal Expert Group
- ZEP will contribute to the preparation of CDR methodologies via its representative in the Expert Group, Kristin Jordal, and by responding to future potential calls for inputs.

3. ETIP-ZEP and IWG9 – Committees and Working Groups

The Committees and Working Groups of ETIP-ZEP and IWG9 form the backbone of both entities.

3.1 Advisory Council (AC) and IWG9 Plenary

The main meetings continue to be the **Advisory Council (AC)** and **IWG9 Plenary** which gather quarterly in March, June, September, and December. The current SSZEPIWG9 grant runs until June 2025. The AC and IWG9 Plenary will therefore be scheduled for March and June as planned, with hybrid meetings in Brussels to be scheduled. Following the completion of the grant, it is envisaged that the AC and IWG9 Plenary meetings for September and December 2025 will be organized as scheduled, pending approval from the members.

ETIP-ZEP is comprised of three Committees, the Projects Network and the Government Group. The activities of the Committees are planned as follows:

3.2 Policy & Economics Committee

The Policy & Economics Committee (PEC) will organize four virtual meetings in 2025. These are scheduled to take place on a quarterly basis, with dates yet to be set.

The PEC has recently replaced a co-chair (Lamberto Eldering) with a new co-chair (Marta Gonzalez Rodriguez). ZEP's secretariat will organise a meeting with the PEC co-chairs before the end of 2024 to discuss the committee's research and work priorities for 2025.

The PEC will pay particular attention to regulatory and policy developments linked to the upcoming Clean Industrial Deal, but also to the implementation of existing strategies such as the Net Zero Industry Act and the Industrial Carbon Management Strategy, as well as to other key legislative proposals such as the much-awaited EU regulatory framework for CO₂ transport. The PEC will evaluate these plans together with members of the Policy & Funding Working Group and analyse the potential of complementary mechanisms to strengthen the business case of CCS in Europe, such as green public procurement processes, green lead

markets, and carbon contracts for difference. The PEC will also examine initiatives to develop and harmonise standards for CO₂ transport and storage and for low-carbon products. Finally, the PEC will encourage the development of sectoral decarbonisation roadmaps to accelerate the targeted deployment of industrial carbon management.

The PEC will establish a Finance Working Group featuring members of the financial sector. It will focus on the financing aspects of industrial carbon management, knowledge sharing, and actions that policymakers, project developers, and financial service providers can take to facilitate investments and accelerate the deployment of industrial carbon management projects in Europe.

3.3 Technology Committee

The Technology Committee meets quarterly and allows information sharing discussions on technical topics relating to industrial carbon management, as well as updates on the development and deployment of the industrial carbon management market. The TC will organise four virtual meetings in 2025. These are scheduled to take place on a quarterly basis, with dates yet to be set.

The TC has recently replaced a co-chair (Arthur Heberle) with two new co-chairs (Toby Lockwood and Owain Tucker). The research and work priorities for the TC have yet to be set but a meeting with the co-chairs will be organized before the end of 2024 to discuss the priorities for 2025.

3.4 External Relations Committee

The External Relations Committee (ERC) provides strategic guidance to the ZEP Secretariat on its advocacy actions, ensuring ZEP's visibility in policy and public domains. It ensures that ZEP's external activities are aligned with its mission and objectives while communicating ZEP's policy positions as developed in the Policy & Funding Working Group.

In 2024, ZEP's advocacy activities adapted to a slower policymaking pace within the EU, with the European elections. Despite this, the year saw meaningful progress across key areas, including:

- **Policy contributions:** ZEP actively contributed to important EU legislative files, in particular the adoption of the Net Zero Industry Act, the Carbon Removal and Carbon Farming (CRCF) Regulation, and the Communications for an Industrial Carbon Management Strategy, by ensuring ZEP's recommendations were presented to policymakers and decision-makers.
- **Engagement with EU institutions:** ZEP continued positive collaboration with the European Parliament and increasing engagement with the European Parliament and European Commission to raise awareness of ICM technologies and their role in achieving the EU net-zero goals, as well as making ZEP visible and willing to provide technical and policy advice to accelerate their deployment.
- **Dissemination of reports:** ZEP published key reports on CO₂ transport by ships, public perception, and CDR certification, presenting key recommendations in public webinars including public officials and key stakeholders.
- **Digital presence:** increased ZEP's digital presence, improving engagement on social media, and launching a re-branding and website revamp project, expected for completion by March 2025.

Building on this momentum, the ERC will aim to further strengthen ZEP's advocacy efforts and digital presence in 2025. The new branding and website, launching early in the year, will support these objectives. With the beginning of a new EU policy cycle, the ERC's strategic role will be critical in ensuring ZEP's activities remain impactful and fit-for-purpose, particularly as the European Commission is set to introduce significant policy initiatives for industrial decarbonisation.

To achieve these goals, the ERC will focus on the following priorities in 2025:

- **Strengthening engagement with the European Parliament:** by leveraging its membership in the European Energy Forum, but also by engaging with MEPs and their assistants by offering technical & policy briefings and site visits. The aim will be to provide ZEP's expertise on ICM and raise awareness of the role of these technologies.
- **Targeted policy advocacy:** ensuring ZEP's advocacy and communication activities align with key policy files.
- **Coalition building:** deepen collaboration with associations and civil society organisations active in the sector.
- **Enhanced visibility and public awareness:** continue improving and increasing digital advocacy and communication, engage with journalists to provide expert commentary, and distribute accessible information on ICM.
- **Events:** host more in-person events, to facilitate exchange of information and coalition building, in addition to webinars and hybrid events to disseminate ZEP's expertise more widely.
- **Measuring impact:** track key measures of communication and advocacy activities, using these indicators to adjust its strategy.

3.5 Projects Network (PN)

In 2023 ZEP started the PN which will support the many ongoing and planned CCS and CCU projects in Europe. The PN aims to:

- Outline barriers and solutions that project developers have faced with CCS and CCU projects
- Enable real project-to-project knowledge sharing and other stakeholders
- Provide insights to policymakers on the experiences of project developers

The first meeting of the PN occurred in January 2024 at the Porthos Project in the Netherlands which was attended by over 100 members of the community, particularly project developers, financial institutions and public officials.

In 2024, the Projects Network also hosted a workshop on "CCS and Project Financing" in collaboration with ZEP member, ING. In 2025, the Projects Network will also host a workshop in January on CO2 storage site monitoring, in collaboration with the European Commission.

The Projects Network will also host the next plenary meeting in April 2025 in Ravenna, Italy, in partnership with Eni, Snam and Heidelberg Materials.

4. Research and Innovation

The European Strategic Energy Technology Plan (SET Plan) is a key stepping stone to boost the transition towards a climate-neutral energy system through the development of low-carbon technologies in a fast and competitive way.

The Communication on the revision of the Strategic Energy Technology Plan has initiated the establishment of five time-bound cross-cutting Task Forces on:

- Task Force 1: Circularity and materials substitution
- Task Force 2: Research and innovation for societal needs
- Task Force 3: Digitalisation
- Task Force 4: Skills
- Task Force 5: Access to market

The Task Forces will allow for strategic discussion on challenges and solutions for integrating the cross-cutting topics in the work of the SET Plan. They also serve as a collaboration platform on these topics across SET Plan stakeholders. As a main outcome, each Task Force will produce technical recommendations to embed the cross-cutting topic for SET Plan technologies.

In 2025, ETIP-ZEP and IWG9 will participate in Task Force 1 and Task Force 5.

5. Deliverables of the Horizon Europe grant

As stipulated in the EU grant agreement, ZEP and IWG9 need to complete the following deliverables in 2025. It will be a priority for ZEP-C and SINTEF to not delay any of the following deliverables.

5.1.1 Work Package 2: Coordination of Networks and Temporary Working Groups

D2.2c Annual progress reviews and recommendations on the 8 R&I activities

Deadline May 2025. Led by SINTEF

Provide recommendations on the steps required to deliver each of the eight key IWG9 Research and Innovation activities-providing an annual review of the progress and where applicable including recommendations.

5.1.2 Work Package 3: Support outreach and external relations

D3.3 Disseminate the knowledge developed through external workshop events

Deadline June 2025. Led by ZEP-C

Disseminate the knowledge developed by the Networks and TWGs through external workshop events. The ZEP Secretariat will use the data provided by CCSA on external workshop events held in RP1 and 2, and will track those held during RP3.

D3.5 Develop presentation materials

Deadline May 2025. Led by ZEP-C

Develop presentation materials and give presentations at external conferences to ensure that conclusions and recommendations from IWG9 and ETIP ZEP are widely disseminated also to broader stakeholders. Similarly to D3.3, the ZEP secretariat will use the information shared by CCSA on activities related to this deliverable on RP1 and 2 and will track those carried out during RP3.

5.1.3 Work Package 5: Management of the project

D5.3 All obligations under the grant agreement

Deadline June 2025. Led by SINTEF

Deliver all grant obligations under the grant agreement and provide the European Commission with necessary reports and data.

D5.4 Develop the outputs for the work packages

Deadline June 2025. Led by SINTEF

Develop the outputs for the work packages as requested by the ZEP AC and IWG9 Plenary.